

Role of in-service teacher education in implementing TBLT in an EFL context: A case study in a Mexican university

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Recently, effective in-service education in TBLT and continued support for teachers have been highlighted as key in harnessing TBLT benefits. However, little is known about the education that teachers receive in TBLT and how their interpretations and views evolve over time in the classroom. To address this, the present study provides evidence of a group of English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers' perceptions and experiences as they receive training on TBLT during two sessions of one week each over 16 months in a Mexican university. Drawing on questionnaires and a focus group, we found that the teachers maintained positive attitudes towards TBLT as an approach which improves their teaching practices and particularly language learning and student communication. However, despite hands-on opportunities to try out and experiment with TBLT in their classroom contexts, the teachers reported a number of complex, contextual, and influential factors that hindered them from fully implementing the approach, and instead encouraged them to adapt tasks and develop a version of TBLT better suited for the educational context. The study contributes to our understanding of the complex ways in which contextual factors can shape the implementation of theory-based approaches in the classroom, with implications for TBLT teacher education.

Keywords: English as a Foreign Language; Task-Based Language Teaching; Teacher Education; Teacher Role

1. Introduction

For decades, one of the most popular communicative approaches to English teaching has been Task-Based Language Teaching (hereafter TBLT). At the heart of this approach, tasks are used to meet (language) learning needs and thus foster language acquisition (Ellis, 2003). However, despite the teaching and learning benefits of adopting a TBLT approach, its implementation in local classroom contexts is often affected by a number of locally-situated needs and

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challenges as perceived by teachers (Zheng & Borg, 2013). The importance of this influence is that in attending to these needs and challenges, teachers may adapt the implementation of the approach following their beliefs and experiences (Carless, 2004), or decide to fully avoid its implementation (Musazay, 2017). This influence in turn shows there is still more to do in terms of the gap between research and practice in TBLT, to ensure its efficient implementation by teachers in their classrooms.

Carless (2012) and Ellis (2003) explain that the local needs and challenges that teachers perceive as constraints to implementing TBLT are the consequence of having exported the approach from Western countries to developing countries where English has the status of a foreign language. This often results in the pedagogic values and principles of the approach clashing with different practicalities, philosophies, and beliefs on which teachers may put greater emphasis. In light of the strong influence that local needs and challenges exert on TBLT, the role of teachers in implementing the approach has been recognised (Jeon & Hahn, 2006). Therefore, teachers' understanding of the implementation and principles of TBLT is key to the efficient attainment of language learning objectives.

To this end, the importance of effective in-service (re-)education and continued support for teachers have been highlighted (Van den Branden, 2006b). However, despite the need to bridge the gap between research and practice in terms of the implementation of the approach, teacher education on TBLT has been largely unexamined (Van den Branden, 2009). Particularly, little is known about the education that teachers receive on TBLT in Mexico. This paucity of research calls for studies which look at the effects of teacher education on the implementation of TBLT in this Latin American context. In this manner, we will be in a better position to understand (1) to what extent teachers are familiar with the values and principles of the TBLT approach, (2) how teachers respond to training on TBLT, and (3) the design of strategies which assist teachers in addressing local needs and challenges within a TBLT approach.

In response, the present study was conducted in precisely such an in-service teacher education programme in a state university in southern Mexico. Specifically, by adopting a longitudinal approach, the study examines the teachers' interpretations and experiences during two in-service training sessions of one week each over a period of 16 months and the implementation they reported carrying out during the 16 months. Through a questionnaire and a focus group, the study aims to provide evidence of how teachers reconcile pedagogical principles with their own understanding and perceived practical constraints.

2. Background

2.1. TBLT and classroom constraints

The past four decades have seen an increasing interest in TBLT since it promotes several language learning benefits (Ellis, 2003). Because of this, higher education in Latin American countries like Mexico have recently designed policies which promote TBLT as a strategy to move away from teaching rooted in traditional practices which tend to limit students' opportunities to develop communicative skills. However, because of its Anglo-American origins, the approach may conflict with cultural contexts outside Western areas (Carless, 2007, 2012; Ellis, 2003). This conflict has been evident in the research literature which reports the local needs and constraints that hinder teachers from fully implementing the approach. For example, teachers' limited understanding of TBLT, their low English proficiency, and the role of grammar instruction in TBLT can be factors that may deter them from endorsing and thus implementing the approach (Hatip, 2005; Jeon & Hahn, 2006; Loumpourdi, 2005). When teaching large classes, teachers may feel that innovative practices are difficult to implement (Jeon & Hahn, 2006). Institutional demands around, for example, examinations (Carless, 2003; Van den Branden, 2016) and textbooks (Carless, 2003) are also teachers' concerns in carrying out TBLT practices. These constraints are exacerbated when teachers experience time constraints alongside heavy workloads because this may put them under pressure to cover the textbook and thus adopt traditional practices opposed to innovation as in TBLT (Carless, 2003; Jeon & Hahn, 2006). Finally, in some Asian and Latin American contexts, there is the prevalent idea that the teacher is the authority and therefore is expected to tell students what to do. According to Jarvis and Atsilarat (2004), these expectations motivate students and teachers to maintain traditional roles and thus limit them from finding autonomous and innovative opportunities to foster their language acquisition.

While the comprehensive discussion of the constraints (e.g., L1 use, classroom management, target language use, etc.) lies beyond the scope of this article, the above evidence suggests that the implementation of TBLT is a slow and intricate process (Van den Branden, 2016), influenced by contextual factors (Adams & Newton, 2020). In such cases, Van den Branden (2016) recommends sharing intermediary steps and specifications with teachers, enabling them to adopt the approach in their unique teaching contexts. Teacher education plays a pivotal role, helping teachers find "personal value and reward in adopting the approach, can integrate it in their networks of educational beliefs and practice, and are convinced that the approach will be beneficial for their learners' development and their own functioning as teachers" (Van den Branden, 2016,

p. 175). Thus, providing targeted teacher education is essential, allowing teachers to identify and address potential challenges during TBLT implementation.

2.2. Teacher role and education in TBLT

Over the past 25 years, teachers have been informed of their important pedagogical role in implementing the TBLT approach (Van den Branden, 2016). In TBLT, teachers serve as facilitators, responsible not only for designing or selecting the tasks, but also for preparing students to perform them (Lin & Wu, 2012). Additionally, they track “the process of task performance and the eventual outcome” (Van den Branden, 2006a, p. 10). During TBLT implementation, teachers guide students in evaluating their task and language performance. Thus, while TBLT promotes student-centeredness, teachers play an important role in the success of task sequences with their behaviour and intention before, during, and after task performance.

Therefore, teachers’ clear understanding of the principles and implementation of TBLT is crucial for efficiently achieving language learning objectives. Jeon and Hahn (2006) suggest that “a task in itself does not necessarily guarantee its successful implementation unless the teacher, the facilitator and controller of task performance, understands how the tasks actually work in the classroom” (p. 129). This underscores the need for sustained expertise among teachers in TBLT (Long, 2016). As Skehan (2002) puts it, the role requires “a skilful, responsive, knowledgeable teacher who is able to cope with groups of learners and access relevant material as the need arises” (p. 295). All in all, teachers play a vital role in promoting TBLT and the use of tasks in the language classroom (Salmani Nodoushan, 2008). To achieve this, Breen et al. (2001) argue that “any innovation in classroom practice from the adoption of a new technique or textbook to the implementation of a new curriculum has to be accommodated within the teacher’s own framework of teaching principles” (p. 472). To this end, the importance of effective in-service (re-)education and continued support for teachers have been highlighted (Long, 2016; Van den Branden, 2006b).

Given the crucial role that teachers play in effective TBLT, scholars have raised the need for adequate pre- and in-service training (for example, Carless, 2012; East, 2017; Han, 2018; Ji, 2017; Long, 2016; Phuong, 2016). As Han (2018) suggests, teacher training should focus on (1) understanding task concepts, (2) grasping task goals and pedagogical intentions, (3) developing a solid command of task routines, and (4) providing context-sensitive, hands-on, and experiential training. Brandl (2016) emphasises that teacher education needs to “walk the talk when training foreign language teachers. Teachers need many hands-on opportunities where they can try out and experiment with TBLT methodologies in a safe environment under the guidance of an expert trainer”

(p. 435). In other words, teacher education should systematically cultivate functional competence in TBLT through well-rounded training programmes (Han, 2018). Thus, in order to enact TBLT effectively in EFL contexts, sustained and culturally sensitive teacher education is essential (Adams & Newton, 2020; Carless, 2007). Both pre- and in-service teacher education should offer diverse opportunities for teachers to engage with TBLT (Carless, 2012).

However, teacher training often focuses on teachers' familiarity with tasks rather than a context-sensitive understanding of TBLT. According to Han (2018), without a coherent understanding of the approach, teachers may operate with a narrow understanding and confusion regarding the implementation of TBLT. To date, TBLT teacher training has received scant attention in research, leaving gaps in how teachers' understanding of TBLT evolves (Han, 2018). Addressing this paucity of research is important because, according to Han (2018), the quality of the TBLT implementation determines success.

In response, the study examines the teachers' interpretations and experiences during two in-service training sessions. By analysing their responses to TBLT training, the study aims to understand how training influences their decision making when implementing TBLT in an EFL context. The study in turn attempts to provide evidence on the extent to which the implementation interacts with TBLT principles and local practicalities of language classrooms in Mexico. In this manner, we can better understand how teacher education could support teachers in not only grasping the values and principles of the TBLT approach, but also acquiring the nuanced knowledge needed to effectively implement this approach in their local teaching contexts.

3. Method

With the purpose of understanding the role of teacher education in the implementation of TBLT in an EFL higher education context, we investigate the interpretations and experiences of a group of teachers concerning TBLT as they received in-service training. The research question that guided the study is:

- What are the teachers' interpretations of and experiences with TBLT during and after in-service teacher training in the implementation of the approach?

To address this question, we adopt a case study approach, allowing us to delve deeply into the teachers' perspectives. By focusing on their interpretations and experiences, we aim to understand the implementation of TBLT from their viewpoint. Additionally, case study data can provide valuable insights that can

be transferred to other contexts (Lincoln & Guba, 2000), in this case, other EFL contexts.

3.1. Context and participants

The study was conducted at a state university in southern Mexico—a large public institution with more than 30,000 students at bachelor's, master's, and doctorate levels. While Spanish is the main language of instruction, there is a strong emphasis on enhancing English language skills across various divisions to promote upward mobility and job market competitiveness. The university's English courses offered at the university cover a range of proficiency levels from A1 to B2, approximately, eight levels in total.

Recently, the university implemented a university-wide policy requiring teachers to adopt the TBLT approach for teaching the English language. This strategic shift emerged in response to perceived limitations associated with traditional grammar-focused methods and textbook-based teaching. The primary goal is to develop students' communicative competence, particularly in speaking and listening.

The participants were 11 English teachers (seven females and four males), all of whom were Mexican. Their teaching experience ranged from four to 28 years at the university level. They were familiar with TBLT due to prior training during their English teaching education. According to the university, their participation in the training was an optional part of their in-service teacher education to promote the use of TBLT. Because they were taking the training, the participants were suitably positioned to allow the investigation of the research question. Although the sampling may not reflect the entire spectrum of views in Mexican higher education, the 11 participants were sufficient to provide a wide range of informed opinions and rich perspectives on the education on TBLT and their experiences with the approach in the university. Importantly, they all gave informed consent to collect and analyse their data.

3.2. Measures and procedures

The teacher training was conducted by one of the researcher. It comprised two sessions, each lasting one week, spread over a period of 16 months. Although the decision to implement the second training session after 16 months was made by the institution, this timeframe allowed the teachers to apply their knowledge by designing and implementing task sequences, gaining practical experience with the approach in their classrooms.

The training aimed to enhance the teachers' understanding of the theoretical foundations of the approach and explore its implementation in their specific classroom contexts. The first session provided basic information and concepts,

including task-based teaching, the roles of teachers and students in task-based learning classrooms, cycles for task-based classes, and inductive grammar teaching. Following this session, the participants were encouraged to apply the approach in their own contexts. The second session delved into more specific details, such as planning, designing, and implementing task-based language teaching (TBLT) cycles, as well as evaluating tasks and their outcomes using available resources. Both sessions included reflective discussions based on theory and hands-on activities.

To collect data, two questionnaires in English were given to the 11 participants in the first training session. The initial questionnaire aimed to understand teachers' profiles, context, experiences with TBLT, and their grasp of the approach. The second questionnaire, administered at the end of the first session, explored any changes in teachers' views and interpretations resulting from the training. Additionally, a focus group was conducted with the teachers at the end of the second training session, 16 months after the training began. The focus group questions aligned with key points identified during the training sessions, covering topics such as teachers' knowledge of TBLT, their perspectives, implementation challenges, and classroom experiences. The discussion was audio recorded in English, with participants' consent. In terms of limitations of the study, classroom observation would obviously provide additional insights into the implementation of TBLT. However, authorisation was not granted by the university to record or observe classes.

To analyse these data, a thematic analysis was performed considering the research question, the review of literature, and the preliminary analysis. This involved firstly reading through the data and individually identifying and demarcating extracts in which the teachers appeared to be voicing their interpretations, views, experiences, and perceived challenges concerning the TBLT approach in their contexts. Then, the extracts were listed using a matrix, and the emerging themes were captured: (1) initial expectations, (2) positive perceptions, and (3) challenges and strategies. These themes are presented as sections in the remainder of the paper.

4. Results

This section begins by discussing the teachers' expectations related to the approach and training, their familiarity with the approach and its principles, and the perceived benefits of TBLT. In the subsequent section, we explore how participants' perspectives on the approach evolved after attempting to implement TBLT principles in the Mexican higher education context. Most importantly, we highlight the challenges faced by teachers when using tasks to teach English in their classrooms, despite the training that allowed them to reflect on TBLT in their classrooms through hands-on activities.

4.1. Initial expectations

In the questionnaire, the participants outlined their expectations of the in-service training on TBLT. In all cases, the participants' responses indicated their willingness to take the training and learn more about the TBLT approach. For example, three participants said the following:

"I want to learn more about the TBLT methodology and how to use it in the classroom. It will help me apply it in a TBLT class in a more efficient way." (Extract 01. Participant 03)

"I want to find a way to integrate it into my teaching practice." (Extract 02. Participant 07)

As shown in these extracts, the participants were keen to learn from the in-service training, and showed positive attitudes towards the approach. Particularly, the responses indicated that the participants viewed the training as an opportunity to improve their teaching practice and change teacher-centred and traditional practices they claimed to often carry out in their classrooms (see Extracts 03-05).

"The majority of my classes are centred on the teacher and many of the exercises are traditional. I would say that the main problem is me." (Extract 03. Participant 02)

"Many of the exercises they [students] use are traditional and do not reflect on the language use [. . .] I would like to change that." (Extract 04. Participant 11)

"I'm not so sure about the grammar. That's some of my weaknesses. I think that's something we need to work on." (Extract 05. Participant 08)

In the above extracts, the three participants' responses point to their negative perceptions of some of their frequent teaching practices, such as the use of "mechanical exercises" (Participants 02 and 11) and grammar teaching (Participant 08). They also conceded that these practices should be changed (e.g., Participant 02: "I would like to change that", and Participant 08: "I think that's something we need to work on"). Although these three teachers asserted that their teaching practices were somewhat teacher centred and traditional, it remained uncertain whether these claims accurately reflected their actual classroom practices.

In addition to perceived opportunities for enhancing their teaching practices, participants' responses highlighted several benefits of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) from the learner's perspective, as in the following examples.

“Students use the language in a more independent way. They are working and they do not have time to be passive; they are all of the time acting and moving.” (Extract 06. Participant 03)

“It [TBLT] prepares students for the real world. Students learn by doing and this encourages them to use their linguistic resources and develop communicative competencies.” (Extract 07. Participant 02)

“It [TBLT] promotes real and significant learning. There is more naturalness and students are focused on a goal.” (Extract 08. Participant 10)

Taken together, the participants' responses again show positive attitudes towards the approach by reporting the learning benefits that they perceive. The statements reflect some of the current arguments about the learning benefits of using TBLT in the literature. For example, Participant 02 suggests that by using TBLT, “students learn by doing and this encourages them to use their linguistic resources”, and Participant 10 explains that “It [TBLT] promotes real and significant learning [...] and students are focused on a goal”. In fact, some participants indicated explicitly that they were familiar with the approach. For example, Participant 05 explained that “TBLT follows three phases: Pre-task, main task and post-task, and the objective is to make students use the language through real communication”, and Participant 09 responded: “students work together to achieve an outcome”. These responses and those in Extracts 06-08 suggest that the participants had some knowledge of the TBLT approach and its learning benefits.

In summary, what emerges from the results reported here is that the participants were motivated about the in-service training and the idea of learning more about the TBLT approach. This level of motivation in turn suggests that the participants were keen to implement the approach in their classrooms, as requested by their institution. As we will see below, the participants implemented task cycles in their contexts in line with the information they received in the first workshop. Some of their initial assertions about the teaching and learning benefits that they mentioned in the questionnaire prevailed. However, the teachers were able to verbalise a number of context-sensitive limitations which they claimed to have hindered them from fully promoting the use of a TBLT approach in their teaching and learning contexts.

In the remainder of the paper, we will observe how the focus group, convened after the initial training session (16 months later), shows the extent to which their initial expectations and perspectives evolved. Additionally, the focus group identifies the locally-situated challenges they encountered while implementing the TBLT approach.

4.2. Positive perceptions

As we might expect, all the participants stated that the two training sessions in which they participated were beneficial because they were able to understand better the approach and how to design and use task cycles in their classrooms. For example, Participant 08 commented: “they [workshops] helped me reflect on my teaching practice and consider some possible changes. They helped me see the organization of the class, learner roles and how to plan a class following TBLT”, and Participant 12 stated that “the workshops were useful for understanding tasks. I had read about the approach and had experimented with the communicative approach, but now it is clearer how to work with TBLT”. The teachers during the focus group also reported several benefits which they could perceive when implementing the TBLT approach in their teaching contexts, as follows.

“TBLT allowed me to realise that I need to reduce my teacher talking time. I was able to see that in TBLT, the students have a prominent role in their own learning. The language function will now guide my lesson planning, not the grammatical form.” (Extract 09. Participant 16)

“I think that it [TBLT] helps a lot to work in a collaborative manner. Students tend to help each other if they are working in groups [. . .] They feel more confident when they are in groups to express that they have doubts. So, it [TBLT] is helping to strengthen students’ confidence and also the collaborative work.” (Extract 10. Participant 06)

“In the past, when we used more traditional things, we tended to focus on grammar exercises a lot and students were less fluent or they didn’t speak. Now, they can speak more, they have become more fluent. So now on, I will continue using this approach and I won’t let the constraints deter me from using it.” (Extract 11. Participant 08)

In the above extracts, the three teachers point to the benefits of using TBLT in their classrooms and, in contrast, their negative attitudes towards their current teaching practices which focus around grammar teaching—grammatical form (Participant 16) and ‘grammar exercises’ (Participant 08). In general, they suggest that the implementation of TBLT in their contexts has allowed their students to engage in collaborative work, gain confidence and take on an active role in the learning process (e.g., Participant 06 and Participant 16), as well as the ability to speak more and with greater fluency (e.g., Participant 08). What this reveals is the teachers’ views about TBLT instruction as practices which foster students’ ability to act independently and develop their autonomy. That is, according to these teachers, with TBLT, students have greater opportunities

to direct their own learning, they support the learning of others, and they actively participate more in class.

4.3. Challenges and strategies

The evidence above shows that the teachers maintained positive attitudes towards the approach. Specifically, they perceived the innovative practices as opportunities for greater learner autonomy. However, in attempting to implement the approach, the teachers felt a number of context-sensitive constraints and challenges. These constraints and challenges are discussed in the next sections.

In the focus group, eight teachers highlighted a significant challenge they encountered during the implementation of the Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) approach: time constraints for planning and designing tasks. For example, Participant 01 stated that “creating a task is very time consuming and we don’t have time to be honest” and Participant 08 said: “Sometimes it takes time to plan step by step, takes time as all of us have mentioned. So, planning all the stages of the [TBLT] framework has been the challenge”. Due to these time limitations, some participants opted to implement individual tasks rather than entire task sequences, as Participant 03 explained: “So, to balance my time, I make some time to apply a task, but not like an entire sequence, yeah because of the time”. Besides time constraints, some participants reported feeling compelled to use and cover the textbook (Extracts 12 and 13).

“We are using here textbooks, and I know that I have to cover my program, and my program depends on the textbook. I always keep in mind that if I do a task sequence entirely, I’m not going to have time to complete the [textbook] exercise.” (Extract 12. Participant 11)

“The textbook is something that was impeding me to use as many tasks as required, because students always want to work with the textbook. They are more worried about textbooks.” (Extract 13. Participant 08)

Participant 11’s and Participant 08’s statements point to their beliefs about the need to use the textbook and how it has limited them from implementing task sequences in line with the training and principles they received in the workshops. While Participant 11 points to difficulties in using task sequences in the classroom because of the immediate demand to cover the textbook, Participant 08 claims that she has not been able to implement the sequences because of the students’ reliance on the textbook. This suggests that teachers perceived the textbook as a challenge because they felt the need to cover it in order to respond to institutional requirements (“I have to cover my program”) and student expectations (“students always want to work with the textbook”).

Because of this perceived challenge, six teachers reported that they decided to adapt some material that they had in the textbook, for example:

“I always adapt things for my students than what’s there proposed in the textbook. We can do it; we can design a task but that’s a lot of work and it requires a lot of time.” (Extract 14. Participant 12)

“I think if we have this task, but we have a textbook, we can also adapt the material from the textbook. It’s very time consuming and I felt like I’ve been lost.” (Extract 15. Participant 06)

The teachers’ responses point to beliefs about the textbook as a constraint for them to efficiently implement task sequences in the classroom. Moreover, in “that requires a lot of time” (Participant 03), “it requires a lot of time” (Participant 12) and “it’s very time consuming” (Participant 06), the teachers’ responses return to the challenge discussed above regarding time constraints on efficiently using tasks in the classroom. Interestingly, it seems that when their perceptions of the time constraints combined with their perceived immediate need to use and cover the textbook, the teachers claimed that they decided to adapt tasks following the textbook.

Another important challenge that seven teachers claimed to face in the classroom is related to class size. The participants reported that the large size of their classes hindered them from implementing tasks in line with their beliefs about how tasks should be implemented in the classroom. The responses of another eight teachers centred on reporting how the use of tasks in the classroom was perceived as difficult by some students (Extracts 16-18).

“It is true that there are some students who get close to me and say: “teacher, for me it’s difficult, could you lead me through there?” (Extract 16. Participant 01)

“The students become shy [sic], so you have to involve them, but sometimes it [use of tasks] is kind of difficult. For some of them it is easy to do the task, for others don’t.” (Extract 17. Participant 08)

“Everything is difficult. To everyone is [sic] difficult, but at the end I think we can make them at least to raise the level a little bit more than the way they started.” (Extract 18. Participant 10)

The three statements suggest that during the implementation of tasks, some students perceived them as difficult classroom activities. By saying: “could you lead me through there?” (Participant 01) and “you have to involve them” (Participant 08), the two teachers express the importance of guiding and supporting students during the implementation of tasks. Besides the students’

perceptions of tasks as difficult, the teachers felt that students' perceptions of tasks as not pedagogic activities were also a challenge for implementing tasks, as follows.

"I feel that they think that I am not doing my job. When I get close to them and I see that they are talking in Spanish, I feel like frustration because they are not responsible of [sic] their own learning [. . .] I try to convince them, persuade them." (Extract 19. Participant 15)

"I remember that some of the girls they told me at the end, "teacher, why are you treating us/it like a primary school?" because I brought that school a big box of presents, they have to decorate them, and they have to design a present for their family." (Extract 20. Participant 11)

While Participant 15 pointed to difficulties in engaging the students in the tasks and using the target language, Participant 11 reported that her students complained about the use of tasks, suggesting negative attitudes towards them and their perception as not useful material. In general, the above extracts suggest that their students perceived tasks in a negative way. As suggested by Participant 15, these student perceptions appear to have motivated high levels of frustration. Even though the teachers felt that their students' perceptions of tasks as difficult were a challenge, some of the teachers' responses still indicated positive attitudes towards the use of tasks (e.g., Participant 10 suggests that by using tasks, "we can make them at least to raise the level a little bit more" in Extract 21). As we will see in the remainder of this paper, the perceptual data suggest that the teachers envisioned some strategies which could help them better incorporate the TBLT approach in their contexts. This in turn shows that in spite of the challenges that they claimed to face, they were still keen to continue implementing tasks with the use of contextual strategies.

In the focus groups, the majority of the participants suggested strategies which they think could enable them to better implement tasks in line with the principles that they have internalised. The participants believed that they needed to develop more experience with the approach (e.g., Participant 06 commented: "I need to work a little bit more with this approach in the classroom"). Moreover, they felt that they needed to make some changes in their teaching practice in order to better incorporate the TBLT approach (Participant 03 said: "I have to change my approach and be more dynamic in class"). One of the recurrent strategies during the focus group was related to the need to improve their planning, as follows.

"I have to improve my planning and design classes based on tasks and real products." (Extract 21. Participant 01)

“I have to be more straightforward when I plan my class following the suggestions from the training sessions.” (Extract 22. Participant 08)

The teachers’ focus on the need to improve their planning practices aligns with the perception, previously discussed, of time constraints when planning and designing tasks. It is therefore important that teachers during in-service teacher training should be assisted in developing strategies for planning task sequences which follow current TBLT principles. Importantly, because the participants claimed to face time constraints in planning and design tasks, some participants suggested creating and sharing tasks among themselves.

“According to the levels, we need to create tasks among ourselves [teachers] because creating a task is very time consuming and we don’t have time to be honest.” (Extract 23. Participant 11)

“We can put them [tasks] together according to the levels of English that we are teaching and make something like a bank of tasks according to the level. Teacher practice is sharing. With Participant 03, I have shared some tasks. We did that and I wanted to share it with you.” (Extract 24. Participant 03)

Participant 11’s and Participant 03’s suggestions show that teachers may devise strategies which are better suited to their contexts in order to carry out practices which are in line with the principles that they believe in. Therefore, it seems that teachers need to be assisted in getting familiar with different resources which they can use to select or design tasks. Moreover, as a way to address the student-related challenges, the participants agreed that they have to implement strategies to change students’ perceptions regarding the use of tasks, as in the following examples.

“We need to help them, monitor them, motivate them. We need this learner-centred approach and guide them during the use of language, so they can discover the language by themselves.” (Extract 27. Participant 02)

“We have to focus on is what students are used to, because we made them get used to receiving the grammar form, target linguistic form, and then they produce. We have to start changing their mindset, but I think we have just started to change ourselves.” (Extract 28. Participant 07)

Participant 02 suggests that students should be provided with support during the implementation of tasks. This reflects some of the content of the workshops in which the teachers were taught how to scaffold student participation during tasks. Then, it seems possible that teachers need more experience in using

tasks, so they develop better ways to scaffold the participation that they expect from students during tasks. In Extract 28, Participant 07 suggests that they have to start changing students' perceptions about tasks. There is, therefore, a definite need for not only training teachers to use recent learner-centred and communicative approaches, but also educating students about the approaches, so they become familiar with them, and they endorse them as useful methodologies for learning the language.

The goal of the Results section is to present the main findings of the research without deducing their meaning. Here, the grouped data and the results of the statistical analyses carried out are included. Figures, tables and graphs are also placed here, as well as a summary or description of the data. Information such as the subjects' average scores or ratings and how the scores varied among the different groups should also be included in this section. The Results section should always be presented in a systematic way following the sequence of the Methods section on which the results are based (in other words—includes subsections that describe the answer to a particular experimental procedure that was elaborated in the Method section refers to the experimental protocols described in the Methods section). It's often helpful to use tables describing results, especially when the author has a lot of data to report (such as means and standard deviations) or is describing correlations. Sometimes it is helpful to remind the reader of the hypothesis before presenting each result. It is also a good idea to tell the reader what type of data analysis was done (e.g., correlation, ANOVA) before it is presented.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The present study was conducted during two in-service training sessions of one week each over a period of 16 months. It aimed to explore a group of EFL teachers' interpretations, experiences, and the reported implementation during the in-service training. At the beginning of the training, it was possible to observe the value that the teachers saw in TBLT as an opportunity to improve their EFL teaching. Their perceptions aligned with the Mexican university's policy to encourage a shift from traditional teaching practices to a more communicative approach using TBLT. The participants maintained positive attitudes towards the benefits of this approach for maximising English language learning.

After 16 months, during the second training session, the teachers continued to express positive attitudes towards the in-service training and the implementation of the TBLT approach in their teaching contexts. For example, the teachers positively perceived how the approach enhanced students' collaborative work, confidence, active role in the learning process, and speaking opportunities. In general, the evidence suggests that the teachers

maintained positive attitudes towards the approach during the two in-service training sessions because they believed that TBLT could improve not only their teaching quality but also students' opportunities to direct their own learning, support others, and actively participate more in class. However, at the end of the second training, the teachers reported locally-situated needs and challenges that hindered them from fully implementing TBLT in line with its pedagogical principles and the training they received. Namely, the main needs and challenges included: (1) class time constraints to plan and design tasks, (2) the need to cover the textbook to meet institutional requirements and student expectations, (3) large class sizes, and (4) students' perceptions of tasks as difficult and non-pedagogic activities.

An increasing number of studies originating from Asia and the Middle East show how teachers perceived contextual factors as limitations to implement TBLT. For example, Carless (2004) investigated the experiences of a group of English teachers concerning the implementation of TBLT in secondary schools. The teachers reported similar limiting factors as in this study, for example, class time constraints, large class sizes, and the role of examinations (see also Carless, 2007; Lin & Wu, 2012; Phuong, 2016). More evidence on the influence that large class size exerts on the implementation of TBLT comes from Xiongyong and Samuel (2011), who report similar positive attitudes of teachers towards the approach but also the contextual and practical obstacles to practicing TBLT in Iran and China, respectively. In 2004, Carless conducted a study which showed the influential role of students' perceptions on tasks as not pedagogic tasks. Also, Ji (2017) highlighted the concerns of teachers regarding the discrepancy between tasks and the content of the textbook, which subsequently influenced the implementation of TBLT. Besides large class sizes, class time constraints, learners' misunderstanding of tasks, and the textbook, Zheng and Borg (2014) and Lin and Wu (2012) found that the absence of effective classroom management, the pressure of examinations, the language proficiency of students, the teachers' limited understanding of the approach, and a rigid syllabus can be also factors that impact on teachers' decisions about TBLT in China and Taiwan, respectively. The findings from this study affirm that the execution of TBLT in the Mexican higher education context can be a complex process (Van den Branden, 2016), subject to a multitude of factors that vary depending on their unique characteristics.

The data not only illustrates how teachers may view contextual factors as constraints to the implementation of TBLT, but also how they reconcile these perceived limitations with the pedagogical principles of TBLT. This reconciliation was achieved through their own understanding and by making necessary adaptations to the approach, particularly in the use of tasks in their classrooms. For example, due to time constraints, some participants chose to implement a single task instead of a sequence of tasks, as was instructed during

the training. Also, because of the need to cover the textbook, other participants decided to adapt tasks in line with the textbook. These adaptations suggest that the teachers, while facing perceived challenges, felt compelled to modify tasks to address immediately relevant classroom constraints, yet still managed to adhere to some of the TBLT principles that they received in the training.

In responding to East's (2022a) and Bygate's (2020) call for research on teacher education on TBLT, this study found that the local factors perceived by the teachers exerted strong influence on their decision making regarding TBLT implementation in their classrooms. This is intriguing because teacher education has been considered as a strategy for teachers to adopt innovation (see, for example, Bygate; 2020; Carless, 2012; East, 2017, 2022a, 2022b; Phuong, 2016). According to Carless (2012), it is difficult for teachers to adopt any innovative teaching approach, like TBLT. He explains that the main barriers facing innovation could be the lack of teachers' ownership, their lack of understanding concerning the innovation, and the change not congruent with teacher values and beliefs. Moreover, the fact that the teachers were unable to implement TBLT in line with their beliefs about pedagogical principles and particularly the in-service training they were receiving may suggest that their beliefs and understandings of the approach may have played a significant role.

This is supported by East (2017) and Pajares (1993) who claim that teacher beliefs may act as filters of new information and experiences, thus influencing their interpretations and TBLT practices. In other words, it can thus be suggested that the beliefs about the locally-situated needs and challenges that the teachers constructed during the implementation interacted with the pedagogic principles that they held about the approach, thus having an impact on the adaptations that they claim to make to task sequences. Because the participants claim to value TBLT despite the contextual challenges that they faced, this suggests that it is not sufficient that in-service teacher education helps teachers accommodate TBLT within the teacher's own framework of teaching principles, as suggested by Breen et al. (2001). Instead, teachers should be assisted in receiving not only effective in-service (re)education, but also continued support (Van den Branden, 2006b).

It may therefore be the case that further continued support and coaching within classroom contexts should be provided to the Mexican teachers who participated in the study (Bygate; 2020; East, 2022a, 2022b). This is also borne out in the data which showed that the participants express their desire to receive further training on not only gaining more experience with TBLT, but also on how develop task sequences and scaffold student participation during tasks. Also, as a way to respond to class time constraints and the concern to cover the textbook, some participants suggested that they should be helped to

form shared task banks, so they are supported to address time constraints and thus implement tasks as they expect. This reflects Ji's (2017) recommendation that teachers can be endowed with freedom to design tasks based on their textbook content. Because innovation can be difficult to engineer and operationalise in local contexts (Carless, 2012), it seems that in-service teacher education should be conducted in a way that teachers not only gain familiarity with task routines (Han, 2018), but also receive continued support in staged phases which pay attention to theory, research, and practice equally, as emphasised by East (2017).

Specifically, the use of research data can be a strategy for promoting their teacher development in TBLT because this would encourage their reflection and awareness-raising concerning TBLT, their perceived contextual limitations, and their classrooms (Zheng & Borg, 2013). Particularly, research-informed teacher education initiatives are necessary to mediate "a middle path between reframing of TBLT (i.e., acknowledging that more established pedagogical processes may have a role to play) and embracing innovation (i.e., trying out something new and unfamiliar" (East, 2017, p. 414). This approach would also allow teachers to continue learning about TBLT in light of practical experiences and relevant research evidence which promotes a more context-sensitive understanding concerning the implementation of the approach (East, 2017). This approach to teacher education would in turn address East's (2017; 2022a) call for an interface between theory, research, and practice. More importantly, it would encourage the construction of teacher beliefs about the feasibility of TBLT in their local contexts and thus new understandings about the approach can be established more successfully (Borg, 2006), having an impact on classroom practices which are in line with teachers' pedagogical principles.

However, the above shows that the present study was subject to a number of potential weaknesses. Firstly, it was not possible to apply the research-informed teacher education initiatives in the research context. It is necessary that further research investigate the effects of data-based teacher education on teachers' understanding and implementation of TBLT in EFL contexts. Also, because of the university's decision, it was not possible to observe the teachers during the implementation of task in their classrooms. Further research which combines perceptual and behavioural data could usefully explore the interplay between teachers' views and actions concerning TBLT. Notwithstanding these limitations, the present study has contributed to bridging the gap between theory and practice regarding teacher education on TBLT by providing evidence on a group of teachers' experiences with TBLT in Mexico with the intention to inform theoretical arguments about TBLT in EFL contexts.

Authors' Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. Edgar Emmanuell Garcia-Ponce was responsible for conceptualization, methodology, validation, formal analysis, investigation, writing of the original draft, and supervision of the study. Caroline Tagg was responsible for conceptualization, validation, formal analysis, writing, and review and editing.

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References

- Achmad, D., Muslem, A., Yusuf, Y. Q., & Fitriani, S. S. (2026). Enhancing elementary EFL students' writing skills through interactive technology and task-based learning: A study with AhaSlides integration. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 20(1), 47-72.
- Adams, R., & Newton, J. (2020). TBLT in Asia: Constraints and opportunities. <https://doi.org/10.26686/wgtn.12720848.v1>
- Borg, S. (2006). *Teacher cognition and language education: Research and practice*. Continuum.
- Brandl, K. (2016). Task-based instruction and teacher training. In N. Van Deusen-Scholl & S. May (Eds.), *Second and foreign language education* (pp. 1-14). Springer.

- Breen, M. P., Hird, B., Milton, M., Oliver, R., & Thwaite, A. (2001). Making sense of language teaching: Teachers' principles and classroom practices. *Applied Linguistics*, 22(4), 470-501. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/22.4.470>
- Bygate, M. (2020). Some directions for the possible survival of TBLT as a real world project. *Language Teaching*, 53(3), 275-288.
- Carless, D. (2003). Factors in the implementation of task-based teaching in primary schools. *System*, 31(4), 485-500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2003.03.002>
- Carless, D. (2004). Issues in teachers' re-interpretation of a task-based innovation in primary schools. *TESOL Quarterly*, 38(4), 639-662.
- Carless, D. (2007). The suitability of task-based approaches for secondary schools: Perspectives from Hong Kong. *System*, 35(4), 595-608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2007.09.003>
- Carless, D. (2012). TBLT in EFL settings looking back and moving forward. In A. Shehadeh & C. A. Coombe (Eds.), *Task-based language teaching in foreign language contexts: Research and implementation* (pp. 345-358). John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- East, M. (2017). "If it is all about tasks, will they learn anything?" Teachers' perspectives on grammar instruction in the task-oriented classroom. In M. J. Ahmadian & M. P. García Mayo (Eds.), *Recent perspectives on task-based language learning and teaching* (pp. 217-231). De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781501503399-011>
- East, M. (2022a). *Mediating innovation through language teacher education*. Cambridge University Press.
- East, M. (2022b). Teacher preparation and support for task-based language teaching. In M. J. Ahmadian & M. Long (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of task-based language teaching* (pp. 447-462). Cambridge University Press
- Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-based language learning and teaching*. Oxford University Press.
- Giofré, V. (2026). Designing material for ESP-XR: An augmented reality-based mobile application for English for specific purposes learning. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 20(1), 1-24.

- Han, Z. (2018). Task-based learning in task-based teaching: Training teachers of Chinese as a foreign language. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 38, 162-186. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s026719051800003x>
- Hatip, F. (2005). *Task-based language learning*. <http://www.yde.yildiz.edu.tr/uddo/belgeler/inca-FundaHatip-TBL.htm>
- Jarvis, H., & Atsilarat, S., (2004). Shifting paradigms: From a communicative to a context-based approach. *English Language Teaching Journal*, 50(1), 9-15. http://asian-efl-journal.com/Dec_04_HJ-SA.pdf
- Jeon, I. J., & Hahn, J., (2006). Exploring EFL teachers' perceptions of task-based language teaching: A case study of Korean secondary school classroom practice. *The Asian EFL Journal Quarterly*, 8(1), 123.
- Ji, L. (2017). The influence of teachers' beliefs on task-based language teaching. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 8(2), 385-390. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0802.20>
- Lin, T.-B. &, & Wu, C.-W. (2012). Teachers' perceptions of task-based language teaching in English classrooms in Taiwanese junior high schools. *TESOL Journal*, 3(4), 586-609. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesj.35>
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage Publications.
- Long, M. H. (2016). *Second language acquisition and task-based language teaching*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Loumpourdi, L. (2005). Developing from P-P-P to TBL: A focused grammar task. In C. Edwards & J. Willis (Eds.), *Teachers exploring tasks in English language teaching*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Musazay, A. M. S. (2017). Teachers' perspectives on task-based language teaching: A case study at International Islamic University Malaysia. *IIUM Journal of Educational Studies*, 5(1), 62-75. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijes.v5i1.159>
- Pajares, M. F. (1993). Preservice teachers' beliefs: A focus for teacher education. *Action in Teacher Education*, 15(2), 45-54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01626620.1993.10734342>

- Phuong, H. Y. (2016). Challenges of shifting to task-based language teaching: A story from a Vietnamese teacher. *Can Tho University Journal of Science*, 2(1), 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.22144/ctu.2016.jen.002>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2008). A framework for task-oriented language instruction. *Journal on School Educational Technology*, 3(3), 5-16.
- Skehan, P. (2002). A non-marginal role for tasks. *ELT Journal*, 56(3), 289-295.
- Van den Branden, K. (2006a). Introduction: Task-based language teaching in a nutshell. In K. Van den Branden (Ed.), *Task-based language education: From theory to practice* (pp. 1-16). Cambridge University Press.
- Van den Branden, K. (2006b). Training teachers: Task-based as well? In K. Van den Branden (Ed.), *Task-based language education: From theory to practice* (pp. 217-248). University Press.
- Van den Branden, K. (2009). Mediating between predetermined order and complete chaos. The role of the teacher in task-based language education. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 19(3), 264-285.
- Van den Branden, K. (2016). The role of teachers in task-based language education. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 36, 164-181. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0267190515000070>
- Xiongyong, C., & Samuel, M. (2011). Perceptions and implementation of task-based language teaching among secondary school EFL teachers in China. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(24), 292-302. <http://www.ijbssnet.com/journal/index/997>
- Zheng, X., & Borg, S. (2013). Task-based learning and teaching in China: Secondary school teachers' beliefs and practices. *Language Teaching Research*, 18(2), 205-221. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168813505941>
- Zheng, X., & Borg, S. (2014). Task-based learning and teaching in China: Secondary school teachers' beliefs and practices. *Language Teaching Research*, 18(2), 205-221. doi:10.1177/1362168813505941